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EMPLOYEE RETENTION MANAGEMENT WITH REFERENCE TO AUTOMATION INDUSTRY IN BANGALORE

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Abstract

Retaining the employees in the organisation is not only the challenge for the company it is becoming the necessity. Because retain the talented employees will give the growth of the organisation, even in automobile industry. Automation is India's largest industry. A number of factors are running to India's Automation market. Young generation are interested now days to work and also for apprenticeship, Companies are also providing the apprenticeship to increasing talented workers, working-women population. The Automation industry is facing the difficult and costly challenge of recruiting and retaining the best talent. There are many reasons may control the ability to keep talented employees, and it is necessity to know what employees' need and value, that can create the problem to them to stay in the organisation and perform well. The booming of automation sector is the major concern of employee's retention problem because employees now have immense opportunity in their service period and also in different markets. New younger generation or fresher's in these industries are getting lower salary compare to the other market. The objective of this paper is to find out the reasons why employees will (younger generation/ fresher's leave the companies taking small experience and leave the organisations. And also to know in automation organisations what strategies should adopt to retain the employees. With special reference to study of selected organized automation in Bangalore city, Karnataka.

Keywords: Retention Strategies, Automation Industry, younger generation, Salary and Growth

INTRODUCTION

Employee retention should be important activity to every company. So to retain its employees every company should come up with best employee retention strategies. Most of the times employees should know that they are treated with respect and equally. And they are fairly and highest paid for their job. Monetary and non-monetary benefits will add on in retaining them. Proper communication channel has to be established in the company to ensure proper coordination and to reduce misunderstandings or conflicts. And company should develop team building or team oriented attitude in employees so that their productivity in the organisation will increase.

Benefits of employee retention strategies:

- Reduce attrition rate:

Strategies used to retain employees in the organisation will help organisation to reduce it's labour turnover ratio in the organisation which is very helpful for company's development.

➤ **Reduces Cost:**

Employee retention strategies will reduce the recruitment and training costs incurred for appointing new employee in the place of exited employee.

➤ **Good will:**

Company with best employee retention strategies have good brand image in the eyes of public. This help in attracting and retaining best employees.

➤ **Workers productivity:**

Efficient employee retention strategies will increase the productivity of employees which in turn increases the productivity of whole organisation.

Important employee retention strategies to every organisation:

1. Right Candidate for right Job:

Firstly, employer should hire right candidate for right job at right time and at right place. So chances of employee leaving the job are less.

2. Work life balance:

Every organisation must provide its employees with right kind of working environment it improves their productivity, morale and satisfaction level. And also work life balance.

3. Employer-Employee relationship:

Every organisation should maintain good relationship with its employees to reduce conflicts and improve the communication between them.

4. Individual growth in the organisation:

Giving promotions to employees performing well will boost their confidence and makes all the employees to perform effectively.

5. Monetary and non- monetary benefits:

Company should pay employees based on their performance. Pay for performance can be implemented. And give them bonus and increments if they perform beyond expectations.

Top manufacturers in 2013

Group	Rank	Country
Toyota	1 st	Japan
General motors	2 nd	US
Volkswagen	3 rd	Germany
Hyundai	4 th	South Korea
Ford	5 th	US
Nissan	6 th	Japan
Fiat	7 th	Italy
Honda	8 th	US
Suzuki	9 th	Japan
Peugeot	10 th	France
Renault	11 th	France
BMW	12 th	Germany
SAIC	13 th	China
Daimler	14 th	Germany
Mazda	15 th	Japan

Future of Indian automobile industry:

- India's automotive industry has become one of the world's most competitive. India do not produce 100% of technology or spare parts necessary for making a car but it is doing its best as per Mr Vincent Cobee, VP, Nissan motors.

- In India Maruti Suzuki predicts car market will reach 1.97 million units by 2020
It has the potential to earn revenue around US\$ 300 billion by 2026

LITERATURE REVIEW

Employees should be retained in the organisation. High cost is incurred for hiring and training new employees and providing them career development opportunities and job satisfaction (Eskildsen 2000 Hammer 2000)

Dr S R Chary, Prof Harish Kumar: According to them talented employees can be retained in the organisation if supervisors and employees solve the problems with respect to employee attrition.

According to Clarke 2001 employees can be retained by maintaining good relationship and bond with them. The above mentioned statement is supported by Johns 2001 and he adds achieve the mentioned objective organisation support team building assignments which help and give opportunity to interact with other peer group on the job and off the job.

Training can help revitalize personnel. For an increasing number of people, the chance to learn new skills is a significant personal goal for both the career opportunities education can provide and for the chance to do something a little different (Mendonsa, 1998).

Employees want more interaction with management, more self-satisfaction on the job, more responsibility and more control over decisions affecting them. They want their work to make a difference and want to be part of something that matters (Taylor, 1997).

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

For this research, we choose the descriptive research which carried out with specific objective and hence it results in definite conclusions. This research tries to describe the characteristics of the respondents in relation to their retention from their concerned organization. Systematic

random sampling is suggested under this study, every item of the universe has an equal chance of inclusion in the sample. We would take a sample of 100.

Data Collection - The data were collected both from the primary and secondary source. For primary data we were used structured questionnaire with open ended and close ended questions.

Data Analysis - After the data are collected, proper tools and techniques should be used for classification and analysis of data.

- Level of satisfaction with respect to Pay scale
- Level of satisfaction with respect to work environment

Hypothesis Testing –

H₀: There is no significant variation between the levels of satisfaction among the workforce with respect to their pay.

H₁: There is a significant variation between the levels of satisfaction among the workforce with respect to their pay.

Table 1 - One-Sample Statistics

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Level of satisfaction with respect to Pay scale	100	1.9000	1.26730	.12673

Table 1.1 - One-Sample Test

	Test Value = 0					
	T	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
					Lower	Upper
Level of satisfaction with respect to Pay scale	14.992	99	.000	1.90000	1.6485	2.1515

Result: The above stated hypothesis was tested by using one sample Z test with the help of statistical tool SPSS-20, table 1 shows the descriptive statistics of the variable and table 1.1 depicts the results of the test.

The hypothesis was tested with a significance level of 5% and confidence level of 95%, therefore in table 1.1 the significant value is 0.000 which is less than the 0.05, therefore there is no proper proof to accept the null hypothesis, hence there is a significant variation between the levels of satisfaction among the employees with respect to their pay.

Hypothesis Testing –:

H0: there is no significant variation among the perception of employees with respect to their work environment.

H1: There is significant variation among the perception of employees with respect to their work environment

Table 2 - One-Sample Statistics

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Level of satisfaction with respect to work environment	100	.8500	.79614	.07961

Table 2.1 - One-Sample Test

	Test Value = 0					
	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
					Lower	Upper
Level of satisfaction with respect to work environment	10.677	99	.000	.85000	.6920	1.0080

Result: The above stated hypothesis was tested by using one sample Z test with the help of statistical tool SPSS- 20, table 2 shows the descriptive statistics of variable and table 2.1 depicts the result of the test.

The hypothesis was tested with a significance level of 5% and confidence level of 95%. Therefore in table 2.1 the significance value is 0.000 which is less than the 0.05, therefore there is no proper proof to accept the null hypothesis, hence there is significant difference between the levels of satisfaction among the employees with respect to their work environment.

CONCLUSIONS

Employee retention is very important to every organisation. They should be treated as asset of an organisation especially younger generation or fresher's. Employing new employee will increase the cost for an organisation. So retaining the existing employees through various employee strategies is a best option.

On the analysis of employee responses, I have come to conclusion that employees are respected and appreciated by the organisation, employees have scope for career development, working

environment is good, most employees are secured about their job, employees feel management and supervision style is supportive.

Through this study I found that employees are not satisfied with their pay scale, and this is the main reasons for employees leaving the organisation. And employees work should be appreciated and rewarded.

RECOMMENDATION:

- To increase the pay scale of employees.
- Here, most employees are ready to take up additional job. So, job rotation and job enrichment within an organisation can be done.
- To help employees to balance their work life and personal life.
- Like flexible timing, vacations, team outs etc.
- Employees work should be recognised, appreciated and rewarded by the organisation periodically.

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